

Literature Review: Emotional Intelligence and Job Stress in Company Employees

Halimatuzzahro¹, Iga Noviekayati²

^{1,2} Master of Psychology University 17 August 1945 Surabaya

ABSTRACT: Work stress is a dynamic condition in which an individual is faced with opportunities, demands, or resources related to what the individual wants and the results are seen as uncertain and important. Meanwhile, emotional intelligence is the ability to adapt to new circumstances. This involves using the thinking tools as intended, with an emphasis on adapting to the problem at hand. Emotional intelligence can also help individuals build good relationships with other people, because they are able to read and respond to emotions better. The method used by researchers is literature study. The writing of this article was studied using the literature study or literature review method. The results of reviewing literature studies show that work stress and emotional intelligence have a significantly negative relationship among employees.

KEYWORDS: Work stress, emotional intelligence, company employees

I. INTRODUCTION

In this era of openness, the industrial world faces several serious obstacles, including regional, national and even international competition. Based on various organizational experiences in developed countries, it shows that only organizations that want to improve themselves through organizational development can survive consistently. Companies need superior and professional human resources to survive. People as organizational resources have unique understandings, personalities and life experiences, cultural backgrounds, abilities to learn and handle different responsibilities, attitudes, beliefs and aspirations.

Human resource management is the process of dealing with various problems of employees, workers, employees, managers and other employees to support the activities of an organization or company to achieve predetermined goals. Therefore, managers must ensure that the company or organization has the right workforce in the right place at the right time to complete tasks that will help the company achieve its total resources effectively and efficiently (Masram and Mu'ah, 2023). Improving individual characteristics to improve the quality of the work environment, to reduce dependency and motivate employees to further improve their performance (Dewanti, 2018).

Scientists both in the fields of organizational behavior and industrial psychology are trying to discuss the impact of emotional intelligence on work stress and individual achievements in organizations such as performance (Muchtadin Zely Emmely Sundry, 2024). Job stress and emotional intelligence are two important factors that influence employee performance in various organizations. From a gender perspective, there are significant differences in how men and women manage work stress and use emotional intelligence. With emotional intelligence, every female and male worker is more adept at managing emotions. Bar-On defines the emotional and social intelligence model as identifying five components of emotional intelligence that are closely related to dominant personality, namely intrapersonal skills, interpersonal skills, ability to understand, managing stress and general mood (Nasir & Morshidi, 2019).

The concept of stress is due to increased pressure on individuals who are fulfilling their individual and professional responsibilities and trying to earn a place for themselves in organizational or agency life. Stress can occur in every employee at work because stress is part of the dynamics of organizational life. Employees tend to experience stress when they cannot process and adjust their desires to the existing reality (Issalillah & Wahyuni, 2021).

A very popular terminology in everyday conversation. Stress is one of the impacts of social change and the result of a renewal process which is usually followed by the proliferation of technology, changes in living arrangements and increasingly severe competition between individuals (Wartono & Mochtar, 2015). Colquitt & Lepine in Herman (2022) define work stress as an employee's psychological response to the demands of their work. Apart from that, stress is a form

Excessive defense from a person against unstable work conditions. Work stress is also one of the factors that causes high turnover intention of workers. High levels of work stress will result in increased turnover intention (Krismoko, 2024).

Literature Review: Emotional Intelligence and Job Stress in Company Employees

According to Isnar Budiarti in Rizaldi (2021:37) work stress is a dynamic condition where an individual is faced with opportunities, demands or resources related to what the individual wants and the results are seen as uncertain and important. Work stress is a situation where there is difficulty, discomfort, tiring and frightening that will be experienced by workers. Work stress can also be an emotional and physical expression that arises when workers' abilities do not match resource requirements. Work stress has a very bad impact on companies, because if employees experience work stress, their work can be hampered and work productivity will decrease (Sandra, 2023).

To achieve the goals of an organization or work agency, human resources who have emotional intelligence are needed. Human resources who have emotional intelligence are very necessary to achieve the goals of an organization or employment agency (Jeffrey and Handayani, 2024). Building quality resources leads to more desirable studies on the factors that determine increased human growth and development. Studies state that a person's success, especially at work, is contributed by 20% of intellectual intelligence and the rest is determined by the individual's ability to build relationships, self-motivation and the ability to control emotions. Solvey calls this ability emotional intelligence. Solvey maps emotional intelligence into five parts, namely recognizing one's emotions, managing emotions, motivating oneself, recognizing other people's emotions, and the art of building relationships (Kristiyana, 2018).

Emotional intelligence affects performance because if employees cannot control their emotions well it will affect the work results they will get in the organization or agency (Organ, 2015). At the Banjarbaru District Hospital, research was reviewed which showed that there were 3 nurses with very high emotional intelligence with a percentage of 5.08%. There were 14 nurses with high emotional intelligence with a percentage of 23.72%. There were 25 nurses with moderate emotional intelligence with a percentage of 42.37%. There were 13 nurses with low emotional intelligence with a percentage of 22.03%. Meanwhile, there were 4 nurses with very low emotional intelligence with a percentage of 6.78%. So it can be concluded that in general the emotional intelligence of nurses at the new Banjar Regional Hospital is at a medium level.

Emotional intelligence is very necessary for success at work and to provide the best results at work. Emotional intelligence is the capacity to apply an understanding of emotions effectively, including the ability to understand emotions, as well as manage and regulate emotions (Ashkanasy and Daus, 2020). People with good emotional intelligence can face challenges in the PT Semen Tonasa work environment and develop into good people. responsible, productive and optimistic in facing and resolving problems where this is really needed (Rauf et al, 2019).

Sholihin et al (2021) Explain that emotional intelligence is the ability to adapt to new circumstances. This involves using the thinking tools as intended, with an emphasis on adaptation to the problem at hand. Emotional intelligence can also help individuals build good relationships with other people, because they are able to read and respond to emotions better. Thus, emotional intelligence becomes an important aspect in a person's personal and professional success (Al faruqi & Iryanti, 2024).

According to Carmichael in Putra (2016) emotional intelligence is a special intelligence knowledge process that includes the ability to express feelings to other people, regulate emotions to achieve goals. High emotional intelligence helps employees resolve conflicts well and creates good working conditions when intelligence is low. This has a negative impact because employees are unable to make decisions and resolve conflicts appropriately. Emotional intelligence also allows someone to describe their integrity. A person with good emotional intelligence is able to think clearly even under pressure, act according to ethics, adhere to principles and have a drive for achievement (Fahira & Yasin, 2021).

Based on the background and literature review listed above, the purpose of this research article aims to examine the variables of emotional intelligence and work stress in general samples and several gender samples.

II. METHOD

In preparing this scientific article, the method used by researchers is literature study. The writing of this article was studied using the literature study or literature review method. The research method is carried out by applying a literature review approach, namely reviewing research articles or research journals that have previously been carried out. After collecting several scientific articles that have been published, the researcher analyzes and concludes in order to reach conclusions that are in accordance with the literature study method.

Journal searches using Google Scholar web searches. Initially the number of journals found was 50 journals and researchers took 10 journals that were very relevant to emotional intelligence and work stress in employees in various companies. The keywords used by researchers to collect published scientific articles are work stress and emotional intelligence. Researchers have obtained several scientific articles related to the variables they want to research, around 10 studies where the research was conducted in several different locations with general research samples (not only limited to nurses). The scientific articles used have been published from 2015 to 2024. Search for scientific articles that have been published via the Google Scholar site. To be able to study the article, the researcher understands and concludes from the data contained in the article concerned.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Literature Review: Emotional Intelligence and Job Stress in Company Employees

A research requires findings from previous researchers which are intended to test the objectivity of the science that is the problem in the research. The results obtained from several studies that have been carried out previously can be taken into consideration. This literature review was reviewed according to the writing criteria, namely the author's name, year of publication, research objectives, research background, research literature review, research methods, research subjects, and research results relating to work stress variables and emotional intelligence variables. Below are several studies that have been studied using the literature review method, namely:

First Article	
Title	The Effect of Job Stress on Safety Behavior with Emotional Intelligence as a Moderating Variable
Writer's name	Tuti Nur Waheni
Year of Publication	2017
Objective	Testing the influence of work stress on safety behavior with emotional intelligence as a moderator.
Method	Quantitative research with primary data sourced from questionnaires distributed to 125 respondents. Regression analysis was carried out to test the hypothesis.
Subject	PT employees. KAI DAOP VII Madiun operations and maintenance department.
Results	1. No effect of work stress on safety participation was found 2. Work stress has a significant effect on safety compliance 3. Emotional intelligence has no significant effect on safety participation and compliance 4. Emotional intelligence acts as a moderator of the effect of work stress on safety compliance

Second Article	
Title	The Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Employee Job Satisfaction at the Sago Company in Salem Regency
Writer's name	R. Gopinath and Dr. A. Chitra
Year of Publication	2020
Objective	This study aims to analyze the relationship between emotional intelligence and employee job satisfaction at sago companies in Salem Regency
Method	The research method used in this study is a survey method with a quantitative approach. The research was conducted using a questionnaire as a data collection tool. The number of samples used was 30 respondents selected using purposive sampling technique.
Subject	The subjects of this research were employees who worked at a sago company in Salem Regency
Results	This research shows that there is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and employee job satisfaction at sago companies in Salem Regency. Dimensions of emotional intelligence such as self-awareness, managing emotions, motivating oneself, empathy, and social skills contribute to job satisfaction. The results of the regression analysis show the positive influence of managing emotions, motivating yourself, and social skills on job satisfaction, while self-awareness has a negative influence. In conclusion, increasing the level of emotional intelligence of employees can increase job satisfaction.

Third Article	
Title	Flexible Working of Place and Work Stress on Employee Performance with a Self Determination Theory Perspective: Case Study of a Heavy Equipment Rental Company in Bandung City
Writer's name	Ganjar Garibaldi and Neneng Hayati
Year of Publication	2023
Objective	Knowing the influence of the Flexible Working of Place variable, Job Stress on Employee Performance from a Self Determination Theory perspective
Method	Associative causal research uses questionnaires and survey methods as part of quantitative research with a sample of 60 respondents. Descriptive statistical analysis, validity, reliability, classical assumptions, multiple linear regression, correlation coefficient, coefficient of determination, hypothesis testing were carried out.
Subject	Sales employee at PT X Tbk Bandung Branch
Results	The document does not specifically mention the research results. Just mention that flexible working of place is in the medium category and work stress is in the high category, while employee performance is in the low category

Fourth Article	
Title	Does Emotional Intelligence Influence Work Stress in Start Up Company Employees?
Writer's name	Renanda L. Chasanah, Inge Andriani, Firda F. Fatimah
Year of Publication	2023
Objective	Empirically testing the relationship between emotional intelligence and work stress in startup company employees.
Method	Quantitative method using incidental sampling technique and data analysis using Pearson product moment correlation.

Literature Review: Emotional Intelligence and Job Stress in Company Employees

Subject 223 startup employees
Results There is a very significant negative relationship between emotional intelligence and work stress in startup company employees ($r = -0.345$, $p < 0.01$). The higher the emotional intelligence, the lower the work stress experienced.

Fifth Article

Title The Influence of Job Stress and Emotional Intelligence on Employee Performance at PT. Gowa Branch of Esta Venture Fund
Writer's name Akhmad Muhammadin, Ismail
Year of Publication 2023
Objective To determine the effect of work stress and emotional intelligence on employee performance at PT Esta Dana Ventura Gowa Branch.
Method Objective: Method: Quantitative research using multiple linear regression analysis and a sample of 30 respondents, employees of PT Esta Dana Ventura, Gowa Branch.
Subject Employees of PT Esta Dana Ventura Gowa Branch
Results Work stress and emotional intelligence simultaneously influence employee performance. Meanwhile, partially, only work stress has an effect on employee performance at PT Esta Dana Ventura Gowa Branch.

Sixth Article

Title Analysis of the influence of emotional intelligence and knowledge sharing on work stress of PT employees. North Sumatra Bank Medan Head Office.
Writer's name Hilma Harmen, Riza Indriani
Year of Publication 2023
Objective Analyzing the Effect of Emotional Intelligence and Knowledge Sharing on Employee Work Stress at PT. North Sumatra Bank Medan Head Office.
Method Using the Cluster Random Sampling technique to determine the sample. The questionnaire was a data collection tool which was then analyzed using multiple regression analysis.
Subject Permanent employees of PT. Bank Sumut Medan Head Office as many as 116 people.
Results It was found that Emotional Intelligence had a negative effect on Job Stress. Knowledge Sharing has a positive influence on Job Stress. Simultaneously, Emotional Intelligence and Knowledge Sharing have a positive effect on Job Stress

Seventh Article

Title The Influence of Emotional Intelligence and Work Stress on Employee Performance at PTPN XI PG. Gending Probolinggo Regency
Writer's name Diana Mutmainah, Yayuk Indah Wahyuning Tyas, Yekti Rahajeng
Year of Publication 2023
Objective Knowing the influence of emotional intelligence and work stress simultaneously and partially on employee performance.
Method Quantitative research with causal association approach, sample of 60 respondents purposive sampling technique, primary and secondary data sources, analysis of validity, reliability, multiple regression
Subject Permanent employees of PTPN XI PG. Gending Probolinggo Regency
Results Emotional intelligence and work stress simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance. Emotional intelligence has a partially significant effect while work stress does not have a partially significant effect on employee performance at the research location.

Eighth Article

Title Emotional intelligence, Physical Conditions of the Work Environment and Job Stress Production Employees
Writer's name Indriya Tantri, Nany Maryati & Yulita Fitriadmi
Year of Publication 2024
Objective Knowing the relationship between emotional intelligence and the physical condition of the work environment and work stress in employees
Method Sampling used a simple random sampling technique with the Harry King nomogram table. The data collection method uses a Likert scale. Data analysis with multivariate correlation
Subject Employees in the production department of PT. Kayaba Indonesia
Results The results of data analysis with a multivariate correlation of -0.433 with a p value < 0.05 . It can be concluded that there is a relationship between emotional intelligence and the physical condition of the work environment and work stress in production employees, meaning that there is a significant relationship in the negative direction between emotional intelligence and physical conditions of the work environment with work stress on employees in the production department of PT

Ninth Article

Title The Influence of Employee Empowerment, Emotional Intelligence, and Employee Job

Literature Review: Emotional Intelligence and Job Stress in Company Employees

Writer's name	Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment to Plan A in Motor Vehicle Parts and Accessories Industrial Companies in Cimahi City
Year of Publication	Ghina Nur Amalia, Arjuna Rizaldi
Objective	2021
Method	To determine the influence of Employee Empowerment, Emotional Intelligence, and Employee Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment in Plan A in industrial companies in this research
Subject	Descriptive verification method with quantitative data. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the data
Results	174 Plan A employees at a motor vehicle spare parts and accessories industrial company in Cimahi City
Results	There is a significant partial influence between Employee Empowerment, Emotional Intelligence, and Employee Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment. Simultaneously, the three independent variables influence the dependent variable.

Tenth Article

Title	The Impact of Managing Emotional Intelligence and Work Stress on Employee Performance at Pt Mnc Sky Vision Kpp Padang
Writer's name	Angga Prajuna, Febriani, Lenny Hasan
Year of Publication	2017
Objective	The aim of this research is to determine the impact of managing emotional intelligence and work stress on the performance of PT MNC Sky Vision KPP Padang employees.
Method	The method used in this research is a descriptive correlation method with a quantitative approach.
Subject	The sample in this research was all 78 employees of PT MNC Sky Vision KPP Padang.
Results	The results of the research are that managing emotional intelligence and work stress has a positive impact on the performance of PT MNC Sky Vision KPP Padang employees.

IV. DISCUSSION

According to Isniar Budiarti in Rizaldi (2021:37) work stress is a dynamic condition where an individual is faced with opportunities, demands or resources related to what the individual wants and the results are seen as uncertain and important. Work stress is a situation where there is difficulty, discomfort, tiring and frightening that will be experienced by workers. Work stress can also be an emotional and physical expression that arises when workers' abilities do not match resource requirements. Work stress has a very bad impact on companies, because if employees experience work stress, their work can be hampered and work productivity will decrease (Sandra, 2023).

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V. CLOSING

CONCLUSION

In general, from this literature review, it was found that previous research from various studies that examined the variables of emotional intelligence, work stress on gender defined the two variables differently and gender was a moderator of both variables. Emotional intelligence is a special intelligence knowledge process that includes the ability to express feelings to other people, regulate emotions to achieve goals. High emotional intelligence helps employees resolve conflicts well and creates good working conditions when intelligence is low. This has a negative impact because employees are unable to make decisions and resolve conflicts appropriately. Emotional intelligence also allows someone to describe their integrity. A person with good emotional intelligence is able to think clearly even under pressure, act ethically, adhere to principles and have a drive for achievement. After reviewing several scientific articles that have been published, it can be concluded that Emotional intelligence and work stress have a significantly negative relationship for both male and female employees.

SUGGESTION

To optimize further research on this matter, future researchers are expected to be able to conduct in-depth research on various topics and research locations. Because the researcher could not directly carry out research in the field, he decided to use the literature review method as his final work. The literature review in this research paper is of course still far from perfect, so the researcher hopes to be able to correct the shortcomings contained in this paper at a later date, considering that the treatment of these two variables is quite extensive and detailed, further research is needed to eliminate these shortcomings. It is hoped that the shortcomings of this article can be completed by the next author.

Literature Review: Emotional Intelligence and Job Stress in Company Employees

REFERENCES

- 1) Al Faruqi, MU, & Heri, T. (2024). The Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Islamic Religious Education Teachers with Educational Stakeholders: A Qualitative Study. *Journal on Education*, 6(2), 13098-13109.
- 2) Ashkanasy, N.M., & Daus, C.S. (2020). Emotional intelligence in the workplace. *The Wiley Encyclopedia of Personality and Individual Differences: Clinical, Applied, and Cross-Cultural Research*, 485–490.
- 3) Fahira, KT, & Yasin, RM (2021). The influence of emotional intelligence and work environment on employee performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable. *Scientific Journal of Management and Business*, 6(2), 1-19.
- 4) DEWANTI, MP (2019). THE INFLUENCE OF WORK EXPERIENCE AND WORK ENVIRONMENT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE THROUGH INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS CV BINAR MADESTA SEMARANG CITY (Doctoral dissertation, STIE MAHARDHIKA SURABAYA).
- 5) Hidayati, R., Purwanto, Y., & Yuwono, S. (2011). Emotional intelligence, work stress and employee performance. *Journal of Psychology*, 2(1).
- 6) Jeffry, J., & Handayani, S. (2024). The Effect of Work Engagement and Emotional Intelligence on Performance Through Employee Job Satisfaction at Pt Pln (Persero) Sumbagut Pemangungan Main Unit. *Scientific Journal of Management, Economics & Accounting (MEA)*, 8(1), 1388-1405.
- 7) Kristiyana, N. (2018). Gender Differences in Role Conflict, Emotional Work, and Performance of Marketing Employees at Pharmaceutical Companies in Central Java. *Maximrenew Journal: Management, Cooperatives and Entrepreneurship*, 8(1), 45-59.
- 8) Masram, H., MM, MP, & Mu'ah, MM (2023). *Human Resource Management: Building Competitiveness*. PT. RajaGrafindo Persada-Rajawali Press.
- 9) Nasrin, N., & Morshidi, A.H. (2019). Emotional Intelligence (Ei) And Gender Differences In Employment: Emotional Intelligence (Ei) And Gender Differences In Employment. *Kinabalu Journal*.
- 10) Organ, D. W. (2015). Organizational Citizenship Behavior, *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences: Second Edition*, 07, 317-321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/8978-0-08-097086-8.22031-X>.
- 11) Rauf, R., Dorawati, A., & Hardianti, H. (2019). The Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Performance at Pt. Semen Tonasa Pangkep Regency. *SEIKO: Journal of Management & Business*, 2(2), 225-245.
- 12) Sholihin, MF, Hakim, MST, & Fitri, AZ (2021). Developing Students' Emotional Intelligence: Islamic Religious Education Teacher Strategies in Nature-Based Learning. *Journal of Islamic Religious Education Al-Thariqah*, 6(2), 168-184.
- 13) Sundry, Z. E. (2024). Job Stress in Mediating Turnover Intention Factors. *JIBEMA: Journal of Business, Economics, Management and Accounting*, 1(3), 176-186.
- 14) Issalillah, F., & Wahyuni, S. (2021). Analysis of the Relationship between Job Stress and Employee Performance. *Journal of Management Science (BION)*, 1(1), 1-8.
- 15) Hermawan, E. (2022). The Influence of Work Environment, Work Stress, and Workload on PT Performance. *Sakti Mobile Jakarta. Journal of Scientific Studies*, 22(2), 173-180.
- 16) Wartono, T., & Mochtar, S. (2015). Stress and performance in an increasingly competitive work environment. *Pamulang University Management Study Program Scientific Journal*, 2(2), 153-171.
- 17) Soekotjo, S., & Lestari, SD (2024). The Influence of Leadership Style, Work Environment and Job Stress on Turnover Intention. *Locus Journal: Research and Service*, 3(2).
- 18) Krismoko, K. (2024). The Influence of Leadership Style, Work Environment and Job Stress on Turnover Intention. *Journal of Research and Community Service Locus*, 3(2), 126-138.
- 19) Rizaldi, A. (2021). Managing employee performance through emotional intelligence and work stress. *Journal Of Applied Business Administration*, 5(1), 34-43.
- 20) SANDRA, A. (2023). THE INFLUENCE OF WORKLOAD AND BURNOUT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE (Case of PT Lazada ELogistics Courier Tasikmalaya Branch) (Doctoral dissertation, Siliwangi University).
- 21) Prajuna, A., Febriani, F., & Hasan, L. (2018). The Impact of Managing Emotional Intelligence and Work Stress on Employee Performance at PT MNC Sky Vision KPP Padang. *Management and Entrepreneurship*, 8(2), 15-26.